

Magnetic force microscopy investigations of domain wall dynamics in grain-oriented Fe-Si samples

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Abstract

The understanding of the anomalous losses in grain-oriented (GO) Fe sheets will largely benefit from high resolution investigations of domain configurations and dynamic domain wall (DW) processes beyond the resolution limit of Kerr microscopy. This work thus combines Kerr microscopy with highly resolving magnetic force microscopy (MFM) and presents the first measurements of nanoscale domain wall motion in grain-oriented Fe sheets by means of a newly developed approach to dynamic MFM. It is found that the oscillation amplitude of an isolated lancet domain in a small ac-field is independent of frequency from the quasi-static regime up to 700 Hz, despite the known increase in anomalous loss. This new observation is tentatively explained by a frequency dependent domain depth, which keeps the lateral extend at the surface constant.

1. Introduction

Grain oriented (GO) soft magnetic steels with so-called Goss texture are the core materials for power transformers, and an efficient use requires low electrical losses also at elevated frequencies up to several hundred Hertz. The anomalous or excess losses in these materials are caused by microscopic eddy currents connected to the presence of magnetic domains and their reconfiguration during a hysteresis cycle. A deeper understanding of losses can thus be derived from observing the domain wall (DW) processes and by the analysis of their behaviour as a function of field amplitude and frequency. While Kerr microscopy is a powerful and widely used method for that purpose, scanning probe microscopy techniques are usually not considered for investigating fast processes, albeit their high resolution would tremendously help to look at sub-micron domain details or at dynamic processes on very small length scales. We thus aim at a more detailed understanding of nanoscale DW processes by an advanced MFM technique in conjunction with established Kerr microscopy.

The studied specimen is a polished disk of 2 cm diameter, cut from a 300 μm thick Epstein sample of

grain-oriented Fe-3%Si. Its global hysteresis behaviour and its losses have been quantified in the course of the EMPIR project 19ENG6 HEFMAG, and a comprehensive Kerr microscopy study on the domain behaviour has been submitted recently [1]. In this work we present a high resolution magnetic force microscopy (MFM) study of domains and domain walls in the ac-demagnetized state of the sample and after applying various dc- and ac-fields. By means of a new measurement and analysis strategy, we overcome the limit of MFM as a slow technique and present the first measurements of nanoscale domain wall movement at a selected lancet domain of the sample.

2. Static Kerr microscopy and MFM observation

A typical Kerr microscopic overview image of the sample is seen in Fig. 1a. The image is taken in a wide-field microscope with X10 objective after ac-demagnetizing the sample along the [001] easy axis and subtracting the topographic contribution obtained in saturation. By setting the sensitivity axis approximately parallel to [001] (see parallel lines) by a controlled LED illumination [2], the in-plane domains with alternating magnetization to the left

Figure 1: a) Kerr micrograph of a sample region with two grains of slightly different orientation. b) MFM measurement of a selected region at the grain boundary.

and right are observed by their bright/dark contrast. The area displays two grains with slightly different in-plane orientation recognized from the change in domain wall orientation across the boundary (indicated by the dashed white line), and a small out-of-plane misorientation/tilt in the right grain, identified by the presence of lancet domains. Fig. 1b shows an MFM phase shift image obtained in standard two-pass mode performed with a HR-MFM tip (225-C3.0-ML3-R) by team Nanotec. While the Kerr micrograph allows a large overview, MFM measurements are restricted to individual scan regions of a few tens of micrometers. The maximum scan range of the employed Bruker Icon AFM is $80 \mu\text{m} \times 80 \mu\text{m}$. The nanometer-scale resolution, however, enables a precise look on the details of the domain configuration. While the magneto-optical Kerr effect is sensitive to the sample's surface magnetization, MFM records the stray field gradients, and specifically their z-components, emerging from the sample surface. Hence, the in-plane domains are not identified from their in-plane magnetization within the domains, but from contrast occurring at domain boundaries and domain walls, where changes in the in-plane magnetization create magnetic charges and hence stray fields. Thus, MFM contrast can also be interpreted as charge contrast, meaning that it quantifies the effective magnetic charges at the sample surface. The detailed image (Fig. 1b) displays two basic domains separated by a segmented domain wall (DW) in the upper part of the image and a lancet domain inside the lower basic domain, all crossing the grain boundary. Interestingly, the slight out-of-plane misorientation and the accompanying out-of-plane

stray fields or surface charges lead to a contrast variation across the grain boundary throughout the image. In addition, the image displays contrast from small particles sitting on the sample surface (identified in the topographic channel, not shown here). A measurement with inverted tip magnetization leads to a full contrast inversion also on top of these particles, suggesting that they are magnetic and consist of polishing debris. Inspecting the image, one can conjecture that such surface 'defects' contribute to the pinning of DWs in the sample.

3. Discrete field-driven domain movement

By means of a custom-made electromagnetic field stage, small dc- or ac-fields up to 2 mT can be applied in the plane of the sample during MFM measurements, allowing the *in-situ* observation of DW movements. The field is oriented in the vertical image direction, such that for the following investigations the sample was rotated by 90° to align the field direction with the sample's easy axis. The investigated area contains a rather straight basic DW corresponding to the domain boundary of the upper domain outside Fig. 1b. It is displayed in the new orientation in Fig. 2a. Then, a central $8 \mu\text{m}$ long line denoted in Fig. 2a was continuously scanned while a very slow ac-field ($f_{\text{ac}} = 0.02 \text{ Hz}$) was applied with increasing field amplitude to observe possible *in-situ* movements of the DW. No effect was seen until at a field of 0.18 mT (pp) the DW had disappeared abruptly from the measurement area. The field was switched off, and a zero-field MFM scan with the initial $20 \mu\text{m}$ edge length locates the DW $5 \mu\text{m}$ left of the original position (Fig.

Figure 2: Discrete movements of a selected domain wall after application of different fields in the direction of the denoted arrow. For details see text.

2b). From then on, the full $20\ \mu\text{m} \times 20\ \mu\text{m}$ area was scanned and at a dc-field of 0.15 mT another shift to the left ($1\ \mu\text{m}$) was observed (Fig. 1c). With continuous scanning from top to bottom and a further increase in the field, another abrupt DW shift ($2\ \mu\text{m}$ to the left) occurred at a field of 1 mT. Obviously, the large number of local pinning sites hinders a smooth DW motion and leads to the observed discrete Barkhausen jumps. DW motion outside the scan range cannot be observed *in-situ* but can only be judged from the new DW configuration after the field protocol. This is summarized in Figure 3, where one sees that the lancet domains moved to the left as a whole in addition to changing their shape and size. These experiments demonstrate, that a detailed study of domain dynamics by MFM requires the selection of sufficiently mobile DWs (to allow a smooth motion) and a careful overview characterization after the field protocol to identify

processes that happen outside the naturally limited scan range.

4. Continuous field-driven DW movement

Field-dependent measurements have been repeated with a newly cut and polished specimen prepared from the same GO Fe-3%Si sample. Also this specimen contains large grains and a junction with three differently orientated grains are displayed in the Kerr overview image Fig. 4a. Two areas have been selected for MFM studies – an area with only one large lancet domain in grain 1 (red frame), and an area with larger misorientation and thus a dense arrangement of lancet domains in grain 2 (blue frame). The corresponding MFM images also encircle the DWs, which have been selected for further DW studies. With avoiding a domain which crosses the grain boundary and with a reduced polishing debris, the DWs are expected to be more mobile. In this work we summarize the

Figure 3: a) Overview MFM image including the DW discussed in Fig. 2 before the application of a magnetic field. Lancet domains with ip-magnetization opposite to the basic domain are indicated in false colors. b) MFM image displaying the domain configuration after the described field protocol.

Figure 4: a) Kerr micrograph of a sample region with three grains of slightly different orientation (left). b) and c) MFM measurements at the selected regions denoted in a).

behavior of the isolated lancet domain in grain 1. In the following experiment, quasistatic DW motion is probed by applying a sinusoidal ac-field with a frequency $f_{ac} = 0.02$ Hz, much smaller than the scan rate of the tip $f_{scan} = 1$ Hz. Furthermore, the slow scan axis of the scan piezo has been disabled, such that only a line of $6 \mu\text{m}$ crossing the DW is repeatedly scanned. The displayed images (Fig. 5) thus correspond to x-t diagrams, denoting the instantaneous x-position of the DW as a function of time, while the field is continuously varied. Figure 5 summarizes the DW movement for increasingly larger field amplitudes. The analysis of the wall trajectories indicates, that DW motion must still be influenced by local pinning, as e.g. at a field of 0.06

mT (pp) the DW moves further to the right than to the left. For larger fields (0.1 to 0.2 mT), pinning is overcome more easily, and the DW position describes a sinusoidal path, indicating that it instantaneously follows the applied field. At even larger field amplitudes, the DW appears again to be partially pinned, as judged from discontinuities along the DW path corresponding to abrupt DW jumps. Despite these modifications, the measurements reveal a monotonously increasing oscillation amplitude with increasing field amplitude, and owing to the high resolution of MFM, oscillation amplitudes as low as 100 nm can be detected. This demonstrates the potential of quasi-static MFM measurements in periodic fields to identify loss mechanisms in the details of DW motion.

5. Time-averaged MFM for analyzing periodic DW movements at high frequencies

The anomalous losses associated with DW motion are strongly frequency dependent, and for relevant applications frequencies in the range of fifty up to several hundred Hertz are decisive. A nanoscale characterization of DW motion at these elevated frequencies is thus strongly desirable, but the presented quasi-static investigation with MFM will fail, when field frequencies come into the range of the scan frequency. Still, MFM is capable to characterize the nanoscale amplitude of a periodically oscillating DW by a new technique of time-averaged imaging, which we developed recently [3]. It is based

Figure 5: MFM measurements across the lancet domain wall with disabled slow scan axis, displaying the quasi-static DW trajectory. Field frequency was 0.02 Hz and peak-to-peak field amplitudes are given in the panel legend.

on a scan frequency, which is now much smaller than the field frequency ($f_{\text{scan}} \ll f_{\text{ac}}$), which guarantees, that the DW passes the tip several times during the acquisition of a single pixel. Hence, the measured phase shift signal scales with the dwell time, that the tip spends at that position during its oscillatory movement. In case of a sinusoidal motion, the dwell time is largest at the return points of the oscillation (dwell time \sim velocity⁻¹), and hence the peak-to-peak amplitude of the oscillation is identified by the distance between two vertical contrast lines in the measured x-t-diagrams. The method has proven to be quantitative in that the time-averaged phase shift signal can be fully described by the convolution of the static phase shift signal and the dwell-time function of the periodic DW motion with one single fitting parameter – the amplitude of the oscillation. In rectangular permalloy thin film structures with Landau domain configuration an oscillation amplitude as small as 60 nm could be detected [3].

6. Analysis of dynamic domain wall processes

For studying the dynamic DW behavior in Fe-3%Si, the lancet DW described in section 5 has been excited at frequencies of 100 – 700 Hz, and time-averaged measurements were performed according to section 6. Figure 6 summarizes measurements at 100 Hz for increasing excitation amplitude. At the smallest amplitude of 0.02 mT (pp), no indications

of DW oscillation are detected and despite the applied field the DW is imaged as a single line in the x-t-diagram. As soon as the field is increased, the line splits into two, and the lateral distance can be interpreted as the peak-to-peak amplitude of the DW oscillation. This allows a quantification of DW motion with nanometer resolution and now at a relevant frequency of 100 Hz. Similarly, measurements were performed at constant field amplitude of 0.05 mT, but now with frequencies increasing from 100 Hz up to 700 Hz. All data are summarized in Fig. 7, which also includes the results of the quasi-static measurements for comparison. The amplitude vs. field behavior in the quasi-static regime (Fig. 7a) displays the monotonous increase already discussed in section 5. Deviation from a strict linearity are understood as effects of the given pinning landscape, which will influence DW motion even outside the investigated area due to a certain domain wall stiffness. The measurements at 100 Hz (Fig. 7b) show a likewise monotonous behavior, and within the error margin, oscillation amplitudes at a given field agree with the quasi-static value. The same holds for the frequency dependent measurements summarized in Fig. 7c, where within the error margin oscillation amplitude is independent of frequency. These results have to be discussed with respect to the anomalous losses, which are known to increase with frequency, especially in the low frequency range below 50 Hz. The

Figure 6: Dynamic MFM measurements across the lancet domain wall with disabled slow scan axis, displaying the time-averaged phase shift signal. Field frequency was 100 Hz and peak-to-peak field amplitudes are given in the panel legend.

Figure 7: a) peak-to-peak DW oscillation amplitude as a function of peak-to-peak field amplitude retrieved from quasi-static MFM measurements. b) peak-to-peak DW oscillation amplitude as a function of peak-to-peak field amplitude at a frequency of 100 Hz retrieved from dynamic, time-averaged MFM measurements. c) peak-to-peak DW oscillation amplitude as a function of frequency at a constant peak-to-peak field amplitude of 0.05 mT retrieved from dynamic, time-averaged MFM measurements.

anomalous losses are caused by microscopic eddy currents due to the flux change originating from the oscillating domain wall. Hence, for a given amplitude of the applied ac-field, the DW amplitude can be expected to decrease with increasing frequency, contrary to what is observed in these local dynamic MFM studies. A possible explanation can stem from the fact that lancet domains are shallow surface domains [4], which might react to the increased local eddy currents by reducing their depth, but keeping their lateral extend at the surface, when being oscillated at higher frequency. This is similar to the expected behavior of the basic domains, which when excited at higher frequencies and thus driven at higher velocities, resort to bowing in the depth of the sample [5, 6]. Thus, DW motion and oscillation amplitude are preferably reduced in the depth of the sample due to the anomalous eddy current losses, while maintaining larger values at the surface.

7. Conclusions

In conclusion, the newly developed technique for studying dynamic periodic DW processes with high resolution MFM opens new possibilities in investigating the details of anomalous loss mechanisms in technically relevant magnetic materials. In this study, we quantified the field and frequency dependent oscillation amplitude of an isolated lancet DW in a GO Fe-3%Si Goss sheet. In a frequency range of up to 700 Hz, where global loss measurements and common models on anomalous losses

[7] suggest a reduced oscillation amplitude, the experimental data reveal this amplitude to be constant, possibly a consequence of domain modifications occurring below the surface of the sample. These first successful dynamic MFM investigations allow to extend the experimental studies in the future to various kinds of lancet and basic domains to provide data for advanced DW dynamic models and understanding.

References

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